

Reimagining Language and Literature Education: the Perspective of Technologies

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Article information:

Manuscript received: 09 Oct 2024; **Accepted:** 10 Nov 2024; **Published:** 11 Dec 2024

Abstract: This article explores how the integration of modern educational technologies is revolutionizing the teaching and learning of language and literature at the university level. It delves into the various ways technology can enhance student engagement, improve learning outcomes, and address the challenges faced by traditional pedagogical methods. By examining specific examples and case studies, this paper offers insights into the potential of technology to create more dynamic, interactive, and personalized learning experiences for students studying language and literature.

Keywords: educational technology, language education, literature education, digital pedagogy, online learning, blended learning, student engagement, personalized learning, learning outcomes, higher education.

In the light of developing new ideas about personal orientation in teaching Russian language and literature at the university, the emergence of a competence-based approach to the activation of educational activities of undergraduate students of the philological direction appears as a process of individual impact of new ways and means of education on the formation of the personality of young students in order to intensify their efforts to solve the problems of education, upbringing and development.

The role of modern educational technologies is indisputable, in particular, interactive, innovative, activating, at the present stage of the development of the educational process is extremely important, because it is conditioned by the need to create an "innovation policy" that generates new scientific knowledge, allows training highly qualified specialists, which makes an invaluable contribution to the development of society. Russian language and Literature courses, Modern Literary Russian Language, History of Foreign and Russian Literature, Introduction to Literary Studies, etc., are given a special place in this process in the preparation of a graduate philologist, in particular, teaching linguistic and literary disciplines, such as, for example, "Propaedeutic courses of Russian language and Literature", "Modern Literary Russian language", "History of Foreign and Russian Literature", "Introduction to Literary Studies", etc., allowing to form highly qualified specialists, professionals in their field, with comprehensive and specialized knowledge, skills, and intellectual potential.

It is important to note that theoretical works devoted to modern technologies and teaching methods are presented in the works of both Russian researchers: S.Y. Glazyev, V.A. Roubey, V.N. Arkhangelsky, A.V. Superanskaya, L.P. Krysin, S.V., etc.), and in the works of the classic theory of the innovation process I. Schumpeter, foreign scientists - Br. Twiss, D. Tissa, T. Iord, B. Santo, J. Bright, Kr. Freeman, X. Hartmann, etc.

In recent years, a huge research, scientific and methodological work has been carried out in the field of

teaching methods of the Russian language as a foreign language within the framework of this problem. Thus, a review of the scientific literature on the topic of the study (the works of Zinina T. F., Monakhov V.M., Bely V.E., Lebedeva L.I. and others) showed that it contains a description of numerous modern educational technologies, forms, methods, techniques that organize the interaction of teachers and students in different ways, which are aimed at the assimilation of the studied material by students and at the development of various psychological aspects (thinking, intelligence, goal-setting, etc.), as well as the improvement of communicative skills.

At the same time, the analysis of scientific literature has shown that in the world literary practice, "innovation" is interpreted as "the transformation of potential scientific and technological progress into real, embodied in modern methods and technologies" [1, p. 3]. As you know, innovation refers to any innovation or change, the result of which is the adoption of the only correct decision or a whole series of similar decisions.

Innovations, according to I. Prigozhin, from a scientific point of view "should be determined by three minimum requirements: 1) irreversibility, expressed in the violation of symmetry between the past and the future; 2) the need to introduce the concept of "event"; 3) some events must have the ability to change the course of evolution [3, p. 29]. The final result of the introduction of innovations is considered to be the following forms of innovation: embodied in the material and not embodied in the material. The latter form, the so-called "soft" - "soft", manifests itself in the form of an improvement of the paradigm or its change in the system of science, education." [2, p. 176]

The effectiveness of teaching Russian language and literature at the university with the help of modern educational technologies, models and training projects, finds its expression in increasing the social and labor activity of the student, as well as solving the problem of quality education.

We consider it important to determine the methodology of conducting Russian language and literature classes based on a scientifically sound system of applying modern teaching technologies, to make a purposeful selection of appropriate educational materials and types of tasks, to determine their place at different stages of training, taking into account the data of scientific literature.

The advantages of modern educational technologies and teaching methods include the fact that students independently and creatively master modern models, projects, modules, algorithms that activate the process of teaching Russian language and literature. In addition, students' imagination awakens, their observation, creative thinking develops, speech-thinking activity and communicative behavior are activated.

We believe that it is necessary to consider a modern innovative task as a pedagogical situation, during the solution of which the teacher can quickly apply his knowledge in other new situations, with the help of skillfully modeled, modernized, supplemented means of influencing students.

Therefore, the motto "true pedagogical skill of a teacher is associated with a high level of his culture, the use of modern pedagogical technology, innovative technology and pedagogical creativity" is more relevant today than ever. For, despite the solid scientific and theoretical basis, the problem of fast and high-quality teaching of the Russian language and literature on the basis of modern educational technologies remains very relevant and requires urgent solutions.

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